

Primary Level UAV for Tunnel Inspection: the PLUTO project

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Abstract—The PLUTO project is aimed at the construction and testing of a drone, capable of carrying out autonomous inspection of railway tunnels. The project is fully implemented by the innovative Italian S.M.E. WPWEB, in response to a challenge proposed by the French railway company SNCF. The system: carries out the inspection of confined spaces where communication with the outside is absent; creates a 3D mapping to be used for monitoring the explored environment; automatically detects deteriorations through a neural network.

Keywords—Service robotics, Flying robots, Tunnel inspection, Neural networks

I. INTRODUCTION

Inspection and maintenance of tunnels are key functions in maintaining safe and effective facilities in the construction sector, in which a rise in passenger and freight traffic means reduced access time for inspection and repair. The requirement is for a robotic system that can inspect current rail tunnels, identify areas that need repair in order to speed up possible interventions.

Interventions of maintenance operators inside tunnels of subways and raw inspections after infrastructure incidents are time-consuming operations. The access to these deep tunnels are inside the urban space and offer serious problems for maintenance people: parking difficulties, tools supply difficulties. Once inside the tunnel, walking is hard, walking between the sleepers is risky, limited space between the tracks, low lighting and hard work conditions (humidity, dust, etc.)

The key task for the robot is to automatically travel to the Point of Intervention from the docking station and, once there, to inspect (visually) the complete volume of the tunnel with many possible viewpoints, in order to report, as fast as possible, the causes of the malfunction or tunnel impairments. In response to this robotic challenge introduced by the French railway company SNCF, WPWEB proposed an autonomous system based on an aerial robot.

II. PROJECT OBJECTIVES

PLUTO will demonstrate the autonomous inspection of railway tunnels. The challenges that can arise in such environment are related to a number of factors including localization and mapping, path planning, navigation to the goal position while avoiding collisions, usage of limited knowledge about the environment generated from on-board sensors. Moreover, the environment in which the agent flies, it poses many constraints over the type of sensors and the kind of algorithms employed for the localization and path planning. For example, in confined cluttered spaces, GPS/GNSS is not available for localization and cameras cannot be effectively used in low/varying lighting conditions.

The technical challenges are numerous:

- Inherent weight constraints
- Lack of communication and GNSS signal
- Designing controllers for a consistent navigation
- The issue of collision avoidance which is of crucial importance for flying systems
- Severely limited energy autonomy

In order to deliver the envisioned solution, the PLUTO project will address a couple of objectives:

A. Implementation of an autonomous navigation system

Piloting a drone manually requires specific piloting skills and constant concentration by the pilot. Within a confined space this operation is often impossible, both due to the difficulty of manually maneuvering inside a restricted space, and to the lack of communication between the pilot and the mobile robot. There is therefore a strong scientific interest in developing solutions that allow drones to fly independently, without the constant supervision of a human.

B. Identification of deterioration through a neural network for inspection purposes

The use of deep learning for the purposes of automatic deterioration recognition is a recent method. Our goal will be to target the results currently obtained in the best international literature.

III. THE PLUTO APPROACH

The obstacles that have prevented the automatic inspection of tunnels with robotic systems so far are:

- Lack of communication that doesn't allow a human to pilot the robot inside the tunnel
- Difficulties in manually piloting a robot in cluttered environment

To overcome these obstacles, we are not proposing an automatic approach, but an autonomous one. That means the UAV doesn't follow a pre-defined path inside a tunnel, but it is able to accomplish an inspection mission inside the tunnel perceiving the environment, thus sensing and avoiding unexpected obstacles and autonomously generating 3D inspection paths to move the UAV along, in order to inspect a target structure.

A. Scheduling system and mission planning

In robotics there are several models on decision making processes, for building up a kind of "deliberative layer". Our solution is inspired by a hybrid deliberative/reactive robot architecture[1] and adopts one of the most widespread deliberative system: namely the "state machine". In particular,

